

Deliverable 8.1

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Work Package Title	Data provenance, compliance, and integrity
Deliverable Title	D8.1 Report on the community standards for reporting, access and integrity supported in the PhenoMeNal grid; to be disseminated in a dedicated BioSharing page via the project website
Delivery Date	M12
Work Package leader	UOXF
Contributing Partners	UOXF, IPB, EMBL-EBI, ICL, CIRMMMP
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Abstract: This deliverable reports on community understanding and needs in data standards relating to the metabolomics domain. The report also provides a collection of the state-of-the-art in data standards relevant to metabolomics-based analytical datasets in medical and clinical context.

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

H2020 Phenomenal e-infrastructure program aims to deliver a scalable, robust and standard-compliant infrastructure for clinical phenotyping by means of metabolomics techniques.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a landscape of data and metadata standards available in the field, as well as to gauge the awareness and usage of standards in the community of practitioners -- primarily in Europe, but also beyond -- to discover coverage gaps and generally deepen our understanding of the needs and practice. This is in keeping with making clinical datasets compliant with the FAIR principles¹ promoting data reuse and discoverability in light of reproducible research but also to ensure compliance with current regulations to meet patient protection and privacy. To gather the community needs we designed and launched a survey, which was advertised among the metabolomics peer. The data gathered defined the landscape and community feedback which is essential for objectives 8.1 and 8.2 (see below), achieving MS8.1 "Initial analysis of community standards finalised", as well as informing the directions that need to be taken in the data standards development tasks (T8.2-8.4) within this work package.

We report the major findings of a survey commissioned by this work package within the EU Horizon2020 PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure project for the use of Metabolomics in clinical context. The study reveals a good awareness of standards for data acquisition but a fairly low rate standard compliant data deposition to public repositories. It also reveals that spread sheets are still the tool of choice for day-to-day data management for small and even large projects. Only a minority of users carry out encryption or integrity checks in spite of awareness of patient data confidentiality and privacy issues. Finally, and most relevant to PhenoMeNal's mission, the survey highlighted a lack of modern tools to document computational workflows and computational tasks in ways conducive to ensuring reproducible practice. These results therefore reinforce the needs for an infrastructure such as PhenoMeNal while instilling in the PhenoMeNal development the urge to deliver pragmatic and practical yet regulation compliant and standard-aware toolkits to deliver effective and trustworthy data management solutions.

¹ Wilkinson, MD. "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management ... - Nature." 2016. <<http://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>>

2. CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- Define metadata and data exchange standards, along with technical and user documentations.
- Implement and maintain PhenoMeNal reference implementations.

The work has contributed towards the achievement of the following milestone:

MS8.1 - Initial analysis of community standards finalised (M12)

3. DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

3.1. Introduction

With more than 950 registrants, the latest Metabolomics Society Meeting held in Dublin at the end of June 2016 was a resounding success, considering the attendance of scientific conferences. This highlights the prominence, progress and maturity of the field in the last few years. In stark contrast with genomics and transcriptomics, metabolomics can now process thousands samples at the fraction of the cost and considerably faster. Both targeted and untargeted approaches have demonstrated their power as diagnosis or as biomarker discovery tools. Furthermore, owing the limited invasivity of sample collection methods and high detection sensitivity, metabolomics application to the clinics is greatly facilitating health services to patients. Metabolomics proves to be the tool of choice to probe the most dynamic components of the molecular responses, therefore offering unparalleled capabilities to probing biological systems in their homeostatic responses to environmental challenges and to draw a more accurate molecular portrait of pathological phenotypes.

However, such growth in usage and application of high throughput analytics comes with a significant burden in data management. In particular, ensuring that datasets can

actually meet critical criteria such of findability, accessibility, identifiability and reusability (*FAIR principles, Wilkinson et al, 2014*) is central for clinical data that has been approved for ELSI compliant secondary data usage.

The objective of the European Horizon2020 PhenoMeNal project is to build an infrastructure able to provide scalable, high performance and high availability computational and informatics capability to sustain and support metabolomics applications in the clinical context. In order to deliver an effective infrastructure, PhenoMeNal needed to understand the requirements of the community and assess the availability, maturity, overlap and diffusion of medical communication standards on the one hand, and the instrumentation signal output on the other hand. Furthermore, owing to the constraints of operating in clinical context, PhenoMeNal aimed at forming a map of the regulatory landscape it would have to operate in and comply with. Therefore, PhenoMeNal commissioned the survey, the results of which are presented in this deliverable.

The design of the survey was in part informed by interaction with large ongoing European projects: chiefly BioMedbridges² and eTRIKS³, which have produced detailed documentation of their recommendations, some of which are available⁴ through the BioSharing⁵ catalogue of standards, a resource that is also part of the ELIXIR UK Node.

3.2. Methods

To collect information about clinical and metabolomics standards awareness in the field, a questionnaire hosted by [surveymonkey.com](https://www.surveymonkey.com) was launched among the metabolomics community. The PhenoMeNal Metabolomics Data Survey was hosted at <https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/metabolomics-data>

Within the WP8 survey, we sought to engage with all stakeholders in the metabolomics community and gathered feedback on data standards usage, and needs from different user groups. To this end we designed the survey to serve three different broad user groups relating to PhenoMeNal:

1) Clinicians and clinical researchers

² "BioMedBridges: Home." 2012. 16 Aug. 2016 <<http://www.biomedbridges.eu/>>

³ "eTRIKS." 2015. 16 Aug. 2016 <<https://www.etriks.org/>>

⁴ <https://biosharing.org/collection/eTRIKS>

⁵ <http://www.biosharing.org>

- 2) Data managers and curators
- 3) Data analysts and software, and e-infrastructure developers.

The survey comprised 3 targeted tracks, engineered to target a cross-section of users involved in the whole data lifecycle. Each track comprised of the same question set in order to give the opportunity for all to contribute responses to all questions, however we prioritized the sections of the questionnaire to better suit each target group. The exception is with group (3) where we additionally included a table of software tools relating to metabolomics data applications to indicate priorities of importance, as we believed this group being more technically focused would be more readily willing to provide this level of granularity. The questionnaire was calibrated towards the data acquisition platforms specific to metabolomics as well as requirements associated with the management of clinical and patient data.

Three main aims were considered:

- 1) Obtain a picture of awareness of data management standards stratified by user profiles.
- 2) Estimate interest and needs for training on standards, and supporting knowledge management tools
- 3) Identify the main gaps and overlaps in standards coverage and prioritize development needs for new standards or coordination and extension among existing ones.

Several rounds of internal reviews were carried out among the PhenoMeNal standards working group prior to wider circulation to weed out any ambiguity or inconsistency from the questionnaire.

All activities relating to the design of the survey, and dissemination of the survey, was done with agreement from PhenoMeNal WP8 partners through collaborative Google Doc editing, a number of Google Hangout calls, emails, and tasks tracked on Pivotal Tracker⁶. The design of the survey was also, in part, informed by interaction with other large ongoing European projects including BioMedBridges⁷ and eTRIKS⁸, which have produced detailed documentation of their own recommendations.

⁶ <https://www.pivotaltracker.com/>

⁷ "BioMedBridges: Home." 2012. 16 Aug. 2016 <<http://www.biomedbridges.eu/>>

⁸ "eTRIKS." 2015. 16 Aug. 2016 <<https://www.etriks.org/>>

In total, groups (1) and (2) were given 35 questions, while group (3) was given 41 questions, to respond to amounting to an average survey completion time of ~15 minutes. All respondents were asked a few final open questions on their thoughts on the future of metabolomics data. The full question set can be found as part of the survey data release⁹.

We disseminated the data survey through several routes to attempt to gain as wide a reach as possible in soliciting responses:

- Internal distribution through PhenoMeNal partner's research networks
- Announcement in the "Task Groups Corner" of the Metabolomics Society's monthly newsletter, MetaboNews, in their May 2016 edition (>1000 recipients)
- Direct email to the entire member's list of the Metabolomics Society (>1000 members)
- Through the @PhnmlH2020 Twitter account, retweeted by various PhenoMeNal individual researchers and collaborators (links to the tweets in [appendix](#))
- Through LinkedIn professional interest groups including: "Clinical Metabolomics" (934 members), "Omics - Proteomics/Genomics/Metabolomics" (1,650 members) and "Systems Biology" (11,011 members)
- Through a guest posting on the BMC GigaScience¹⁰ journal's blog (GigaBlog)¹¹The GigaBlog guest posting was also promoted via social media by the Nature Scientific Data¹² journal and others.
- Promotion in-person by PhenoMeNal partners who organised or participated in training events at EMBL-EBI, and also at the Metabolomics Society 2016 meeting in Dublin (June 26-29, 2016) that had approximately 950 in attendance.

The survey was launched on March 1st 2016, and our results include responses up until 31st of July 2016 (5 months).

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https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/19LixDb36yQ9j2nkTm0a6ihH2wJG7ZG0a_W7vkV1t0xI/edit?usp=sharing

¹⁰ "GigaScience | Home page." 2015. 16 Aug. 2016 <<http://gigascience.biomedcentral.com/>>

¹¹ <http://blogs.biomedcentral.com/gigablog/2016/07/19/guest-posting-building-phenomenal-metabolomics-e-infrastructure/>

¹² "Scientific Data - Nature." 2014. 16 Aug. 2016 <<http://www.nature.com/sdata/>>

Figure 1. Logic of the PhenoMeNal Metabolomics Data Questionnaire: Peer aligned question subsets are selected based on three main user types (user roles/occupation).

3.3. Results and Discussion

In all, we obtained **132** responses out of a potential catching population of more than 2400 email addresses from the Metabolomics Society mailing list. This amounts roughly to a 5 % rate of response, which is in the average for such unsolicited request for information and consistent with earlier surveys in the Metabolomics circles¹³. The entire dataset is publicly available from the following link¹⁴ and corresponds to an export of SurveyMonkey collected data. Of the 132 responses, 2 had to be excluded as clearly spurious while another 4 entries had to be merged as clearly corresponding to the same users who supplied information twice.

A total of 128 responses suitable for exploitation were collected, which, given the targeted nature of the survey to metabolomics-related stakeholders, we believe is an excellent return. The largest group of respondents identified themselves as falling in the category of 'involvement in data analysis, computation software or infrastructure' (55.30%, n=73), followed up by 'clinicians, clinical researchers, or principal investigators' (36.36%, n=48) and finally 'data managers or curators' (8.33%, n=11). Around a fourth (33 out of 128) of the respondents belong to institutions participating in

¹³ Weber, R.J.M. et al. "Training needs in metabolomics - NCBI - National Institutes of Health." 2015. <<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4475540/>>

¹⁴

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/19LixDb36yQ9j2nkTm0a6ihH2wJG7ZG0a_W7vkV1t0xl/edit?usp=sharing

PhenoMeNal, meaning that the survey reached its goal of scanning the needs of the PhenoMeNal community but also those of the Metabolomics community at large.

Figure 2. Respondent roles by category.

The key findings of the H2020 Phenomenal Survey on standards are the following:

- **Most respondents indicated they used spreadsheet solutions** (Excel) for collecting sample metadata and data (Q24/46/76:77.5%, n=55), followed by custom LIMS solutions (Q24/46/76:31%, n=22). For those using LIMS systems the overwhelming majority were able to export metadata in Excel like spreadsheets (Q26/48/78:86%, n=26), with XML being the second most frequently used serialization (Q26/48/78:37%, n=11).
- In terms of data acquisition techniques, the overwhelming **majority of metabolomics practitioners rely on mass spectrometry** (all types confounded) to perform either targeted or untargeted profiling (Q14/36/66:global profiling: 85.6%, n=83; targeted profiling 67.0%, n=65). A quarter of respondents indicated that mass spectrometry and NMR spectroscopy was applied to probe metabolic fluxes relying on stable isotopic labeling (Q14/36/66:24.7%, n=24). The survey also picked up the rise of imaging application which rely on mass spectrometry metabolomics applications (Q14/36/66:12.4%, n=12).

- The majority of **clinical metabolomics profiling appears to be occurring in the context of clinical interventions** (Q5/61/97:57.3%, n=47). In 34.1% (Q5/61/97:n=28) of such cases, the reported study design underlying the study was of the repeated measure type with crossover. This type of design is frequently used in nutrition studies and studies focusing on metabolic syndromes associated with Type 2 Diabetes. Accounting for **over a third of all study types indicated, and owing to its importance in the realm of nutrition**, PhenoMeNal needs to consider this type of study design with the right level of attention and offer meaningful data management support.
- In terms of **volume of sample processing and data productions**, the weight of the large **phenome centres**, which are being established is showing clearly with **24.5% of respondents** (Q17/39/69:n=12). This indicates processing at industrial scale with more than 10,000 samples processed. **65.3% of data producers fell into the range of more than 1,000 but less than 10,000 samples a year** (Q17/39/69:n=32). This is an extremely valuable insight as it provides a very good estimate of the volume of data PhenoMeNal needs to plan for and be able to cope with. Efficient processing has to be done for supporting current datasets retrospectively and, more critically, PhenoMeNal needs to define methods and processes to enable prospective data management.
- **Data deposition either to public repositories or regulatory agencies remains the exception rather than the norm**. Of all respondents, only a third had deposited data to public repositories (Q19/41/71: 35.9%, n=29) and only one respondent indicated experience with regulatory submissions (Q21/43/73: in other, 1.3%, n=1).
- Almost **half of the respondents indicated that they are required by their funding bodies to deposit data in dedicated repositories with access restriction in place** (Q18/40/70: 48.2%, n=39). Only 10% (Q18/40/70: 9.9%, n=8) indicated they could not release data without any strings attached.
- **Standard awareness is patchy and the implementation gap is still quite wide** as revealed by the analysis of responses obtained for relevant questions. While a majority of respondents showed awareness of the Metabolomics Society annotation guidelines^{15, 16}, which was expected owing the way the audience was

¹⁵ Salek, RM. "The role of reporting standards for metabolite annotation and ... - NCBI." 2013. <<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3853013/>>

targeted, the **survey reveals a knowledge gap for all well-established clinical standards**. Less than 10% are aware of **HL7** standards for electronic health records (Q23/45/75: 9.1%, n=6), the penetration of **CDISC SDTM**¹⁷ standards (Q22/44/74: 11.9%, n=5), well known in industry circles in only of 15% among respondent. More recent efforts such as **GA4GH** (currently involved in the **Phenopackets**¹⁸ specifications) is as low as 10% (Q23/45/75: 10.6%, n=7), in the same range as awareness of the ISBER SPREC guidelines¹⁹, a coding specifications proposed in clinical specimen biobanking.

- **Standards closer to the technologies used in Metabolomics** or those specifications promoted by the Metabolomics Society, in sharp contrast, **are rather well known**. **CIMR** annotation guidelines, **ISA format** and associated configurations have been identified by 47.6% (Q22/44/74: n=20) and 57.2% (Q22/44/74: n=24) of respondents respectively. The figure rises to 75% (Q16/38/68: n=56) awareness in **mzML**²⁰ for mass-spectrometry. In the field on NMR practitioners, **Bruker file format** is the de-facto standard, reflecting the dominant position of the supplier on the market. Only 13.5% (Q15/37/67: n=5) of users mention **nmrML**²¹ as a possible format. This is as many as mention JCAMP, but this might relate to the fact that this standard is still a release candidate and the nmrML paper not yet published. So this result actually looks promising, even if the normative impact may not be as pronounced as that of mzML for mass spectrometry. mzML also remediated the large heterogeneity of instrument output, which plagued the domain and the mzML standard has been around for years. The field of NMR spectroscopy on the other hand is already more homogenous, with only few vendors left to generate proprietary data formats to be integrated via nmrML.
- It is a similar situation in terms of metadata standards. Even with the simple case of date datatypes, **while the corresponding ISO8601 standard**²² **is well**

¹⁶ "The Metabolomics Standards Initiative (MSI)." 2015. 20 Aug. 2016 <<http://www.metabolomics-msi.org/>>

¹⁷ "Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM) | CDISC." 2016. 16 Aug. 2016 <<http://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundational/sdtm>>

¹⁸ "PhenoPackets · GitHub." 2016. 16 Aug. 2016 <<https://github.com/phenopackets>>

¹⁹ Lehmann, Sabine et al. "Standard preanalytical coding for biospecimens: Review and implementation of the Sample PREanalytical Code (SPREC)." *Biopreservation and biobanking* 10.4 (2012): 366-374.

²⁰ "mzML 1.1.0 Specification | HUPO Proteomics Standards Initiative." 2012. 16 Aug. 2016 <http://www.psidev.info/mzml_1_0_0%20>

²¹ "nmrML · GitHub." 2013. 16 Aug. 2016 <<https://github.com/nmrML>>

²² "ISO 8601 - Time and date format." 2013. 17 Aug. 2016 <<http://www.iso.org/iso/home/standards/iso8601.htm>>

established, only 20% (Q28/50/80: n=11) of the respondents indicated they were using this specification for validating user input. The rest simply relied on free text as supplied by users. That alone can lead to a significant burden for the normalization of time related elements, which are crucial in many steps of an experimental set-up, to assess batch effect, account for confounding factors or simply produce a visual timeline of intervention and treatment or visits patients undergo during clinical examination. Hence we included that element in our survey as a marker of standard acceptance owing to its seemingly widespread adoption and support.

3.4. Final Remarks and Summary

A survey was carried out under the auspices of and serving the H2020 PhenoMeNal project and in collaboration with the Metabolomics Society. It was supported by key stakeholders such as major publishers and leading data journals (NPG, BMC with Scientific Data and GigaScience) and targeted the wider metabolomics as well as the clinical phenotyping community. The results highlight the need to bridge an awareness divide for clinical standards and instrumentation related standards. While the latter are well understood by personnel in charge of data production centres, patient-centric metadata standards are less known to that audience.

The survey revealed two areas in dire need of standardisation. The first is that of analysis reporting. Indeed two-thirds of participants to the survey (Q32/54/84: 67.1%, n=47) indicated that description of the data processing was only captured in textual form. This entails inevitably poor capability of automatic high-throughput review, quality assurance and reproducibility of the findings. This is precisely what the PhenoMeNal program aims to have most impact on, as it intends to provide all the necessary infrastructure to re-enact clinical data processing within computational workflows stored in machine readable and runnable format.

The second salient point is a gap between ELSI awareness and implementation. Respondents indicate a good level of awareness around requirements for patient data protection and privacy. However, based on the survey results the actual level of data integrity checks and encryption are extremely low. This points again to the need to implement out of the box solutions in the various APIs beings developed, to provide native checksumming on data files and options to provide robust encryption routines for

data and metadata files to comply with current regulatory requirements for clinical omics datasets.

For message serialization, the PhenoMeNaI project will follow W3C best practices for XML, XML/RDF, JSON-LD and RFC 4627 for JSON exchange syntaxes. For entity identification, W3C recommendations will be followed and URIs²³ or IRIs will be used.

The H2020 Phenomenal list of surveyed standards and resources is available from BioSharing portal as a dedicated collection, which highlights status and uptake for a number of those resources:

<https://biosharing.org/collection/H2020PhenomeandMetabolomeaNaIysisPhenoMeNaIproject>

The screenshot displays the BioSharing portal interface for the 'H2020 Phenome and Metabolome aNaIysis (PhenoMeNaI) project'. The page features a search bar at the top, navigation tabs for 'Standards', 'Databases', 'Policies', 'Collections', and 'Add/Claim Content'. Below the search bar, there are buttons for 'Watch Record', 'Revoke Ownership', and 'Admin Edit'. The main content area shows the project title and a brief description. A sidebar on the left provides filters for 'Taxonomic range' (Homo Sapiens), 'Scope and data types' (Clinical Data, Computational Biology, Mass Spectrometry, Metabolite, Metabolomics, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy, Phenotype), and 'Record Status' (Uncertain, Deprecated, In development, Ready). The main table lists 28 records with columns for 'Record ID', 'Name', 'Abbreviation', 'Type', 'Domain', 'Taxonomy', 'Related Database', 'Related Standard', 'Related Policy', and 'In Collection/Recommendation'. Each record includes a status indicator (e.g., 'Ready', 'In development', 'Deprecated') and a 'Standard Type' dropdown menu.

Figure 3. The PhenoMeNaI Collection of Standards as available from BioSharing portal, also a resource of the ELIXIR UK Node. Each entry in the collection includes a status indicating whether the standard is Ready/In production use, In Development, or Deprecated (no longer supported).

²³ Compact URIs may be used within the context of a document, through the declaration of prefixes.

4. WORK PLAN

The focus of WP8 up to this deliverable D8.1 has been to engage with the community around metabolomics data and understand the needs of the community to help inform the standards development that is to take place in the remaining tasks and deliverables (T8.1-8.5 and D8.2-D8.4).

Figure 4. Structure of the WP8 workplan of tasks, deliverables and objectives.

Objectives

O8.1 Define metadata and data exchange standards, along with technical and user documentations.

O8.2 Implement and maintain PhenoMeNal reference implementations.

Tasks

T8.1: Use cases and state of the art of communication standards

T8.2: Standards for exchanging experimental and clinical metadata

T8.3: Data standards exchange formats

T8.4: Harmonization of data matrices and analytical results

T8.5: Maintain documentation and disseminate information

Deliverables

D8.1 Report on community standards for reporting, access and integrity supported in the PhenoMeNal grid; to be disseminated in a dedicated BioSharing page and via the project website. (M12)

D8.2: Modularized ISA model and format: biospecimen centric schema, corresponding xml schemas, reference implementation guidelines and validation rules. (M24)

D8.3: nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules. (M18)

D8.4: Signal processing and analysis data exchange format

D8.4.1: specifications for derived data matrices specifications and terminology for description of analysis and statistical results (M24)

D8.4.2: reference implementation guidelines and validation rules (M30)

Broadly the remaining tasks aim to:

- Once use case workflows are implemented, detect coverage gaps and overlaps in existing clinical standards
- To develop a set of modular community-agreed format specifications to achieve required domain coverage and assuring maximum efficiency during data exchange.
- Address the range of distinct data management scenarios as well as complimentary use cases (including consideration for data safety/patient de-identification).
- While supporting multiple data management modules, retaining compatibility with existing community standards.
- Coordinate between namespace borders in order to avoid overlapping, non-orthogonal ontologies and standards in order to save users from heterogeneous annotations.

The next key deliverable is on D8.3 “nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules” at M18, and D8.2 “Modularized ISA model and format:

biospecimen centric schema, corresponding xml schemas, reference implementation guidelines and validation rules” at M24. Work towards these has already begun (progress can be found in Pivotal tracker), with much work towards the reference implementations and tooling underway in collaboration with WP9.

The current state of WP8 tasks is documented in the below screenshots taken from the PhenoMeNal Pivotal tracker, which records live progress.

The figure displays three screenshots of the PhenoMeNal Pivotal Tracker interface. The leftmost screenshot shows a list of tasks for 'Wp8' (42 stories, 89 points). The middle screenshot shows a detailed view of a task 'D8.1 - Report on community standards for reporting, access and integrity supported in the PhenoMeNal grid; to be disseminated in a dedicated BioSharing page and via the project website (PRS, DJ)'. The rightmost screenshot shows a detailed view of a task 'Icebox stories' (42 stories, 89 points) with a list of sub-tasks and their status.

Wp8 (42 stories, 89 points)

- Draft Data Standards Survey (DJ, PRS) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Finalize Data Standards Survey in SurveyMonkey (PRS, DJ) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Draft text about survey for MetaboNews (PRS, DJ) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Disseminate survey via MetaboNews (March) (PRS, RS, DJ) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Publish and disseminate Data Standards Survey (PRS, DJ) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Disseminate survey via MetaboNews (May) (PRS, RS, DJ) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- ISA converters microservices (DJ) (isa, microservice, wp5, wp8)
- ISA JSON validator (DJ) (isa, uoxf, wp8)
- ISA tab validator (replaces legacy validator) (DJ) (isa, uoxf, wp8)
- WP8 slides for SAB meeting (DJ) (outreach, wp8)
- Disseminate data survey to LinkedIn groups (DJ) (outreach, wp8)
- ISA JSON validator microservice (DJ) (isa, microservice, uoxf, wp8)
- ISA tab validator microservice (DJ) (isa, microservice, uoxf, wp8)
- Email blast of survey to MetSoc (RS, DJ, PRS) (survey, wp8)
- Organise ISA-NPC meeting (DJ, PRS) (icl, isa, meeting, uoxf, wp8)
- Advertise about survey via NPG Scientific Data (DJ, PRS) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Guest blog for GigaScience (DJ, PRS) (outreach, survey, wp8)
- Add ISA validator microservices to Jenkins (DJ) (docker, microservice, wp8)

Wp8 (42 stories, 89 points)

- D8.1 - Report on community standards for reporting, access and integrity supported in the PhenoMeNal grid; to be disseminated in a dedicated BioSharing page and via the project website (PRS, DJ) (cirmmp, embi-ebi, icl, ipb, m12, uoxf, wp8, year1) (Finish)
- Review MTBLS content for work on data matrices (PRS) (wp8) (Finish)
- MW2ISA converter (KH, PRS, DJ) (isa, metabolomicsworkbench, wp8) (Finish)
- Organise PhenoMeNal Data-thon (DJ, PRS) (meeting, outreach, wp8) (Finish)
- Technical Proof-of-Concept manuscript (OS, MC, CS) (wp5, wp8, wp9) (Finish)
- Script for pulling from MTBLS for use in ISA API (DJ) (isa, metabollights, wp8) (Finish)
- Analyze data survey data (DJ) (survey, uoxf, wp8) (Finish)

Wp8 (42 stories, 89 points)

Icebox stories

- Create BioSharing collection based on survey (survey, uoxf, wp8) (Start)
- Collate data survey data (survey, uoxf, wp8) (Start)
- Disseminate survey via MetaboNews (June) (PRS, RS) (outreach, survey, wp8) (Start)
- Collate and analyze Data Standards Survey responses (outreach, survey, wp8) (Start)
- Close Data Standards Survey (outreach, survey, wp8) (Start)
- Data Sharing and Standards Workshop 2 (DJ, PRS) (meeting, outreach, wp8) (Start)
- linkedISA microservice (isa, microservice, wp8) (Start)
- Develop Jupyter notebooks for ISA microservice demos (DJ) (isa, microservice, wp8) (Start)
- rISA microservice (isa, microservice, wp8) (Start)
- Galaxy plugin for ISA (galaxy, isa, wp8) (Start)
- ISA-Tab as a data type in Galaxy (galaxy, wp8) (Start)
- Information classification of metabolomics data (GLEN, DJ) (icl, uu, wp7, wp8) (Start)
- D8.2 - Modularized ISA model and format: biospecimen centric schema, corresponding xml schemas, reference implementation guidelines and validation rules. (PRS) (bbmrl, cea, cirmmp, crs4, embi-ebi, icl, inra, ipb, m24, sib, ub, ul, uob, uoxf, uu, wp8, year2) (Start)
- D8.3 - nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules (PRS) (bbmrl, cea, cirmmp, crs4, embi-ebi, icl, inra, ipb, m18, sib, ub, ul, uob, uoxf, uu, wp8, year2) (Start)

Figure 5. Screen capture of the PhenoMeNal Pivotal Tracker Feed used to organise tasks and track progress.

Utilization of Resources

Total person month (PMs) contribution until M12 (inclusive)

Partners	ICL	IPB	CRIMMP	UOXF	UU
PMs	1	2	0.5	5	2.55

5. DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

The delivery is delayed: No

6. CONCLUSION

The work done towards T8.1, “Use cases and state-of-the-art of communication standards” and reported on in this deliverable includes the commissioning and execution of a community-wide survey on metabolomics data needs, the PhenoMeNal Data Infrastructures Survey, and the collation of the state-of-the-art in relevant data standards, the PhenoMeNal Data Standards Collection. Much insight was found in the survey results helping to shape the data standards collection, but also to help inform the future work that needs to be carried out in WP8. In particular, the upcoming tasks and deliverables now focus on standards development and adoption within the PhenoMeNal use cases, with ISA, mzML, and nmrML being further developed for use by the metabolomics community.

7. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL: STANDARDS LANDSCAPE RELEVANT TO PHENOMENAL

A.1. Metabolomics Data Standards, Formats and Specifications

Name	Abbreviation	Type	Development Group	Description	Domain	Status
Core Information for Metabolomics Reporting	CIMR	Annotation Guideline	MSI Initiative	This document specifies the minimal guidelines reporting metabolomics work. It does so in a textual form and seeks in the long term to cover all application areas and analysis technologies.	From Study Design to Data	Released
Investigation Study Assay Tabular	ISA-Tab	Syntax Specification	ISA community	General-purpose ISA-Tab file format - an extensible, hierarchical structure	Study and Experiment Metadata	Released, in production

				that focuses on the description of the experimental metadata (i.e. sample characteristics, technology and measurement types, sample-to-data relationships).		
Analytical Information Markup Language	AniML	Syntax Specification	American Society for Testing and Materials	AniML aims to provide a generic data container that can hold experimental data from any analytical technique, while at the same time permitting the formal delineation of technique-	experimental data from any analytical technique	Pre-release form

				<p>specific constraints for using this data container, i.e., how the data for specific measurement techniques should be captured represented in the data file. This will allow collection of relevant analytical data in a single place, even for complex workflows using multiple, different analytical techniques</p>		
<p>mz Markup Language</p>	<p>mzML</p>	<p>Syntax Specification</p>	<p>HUPO-PSI initiative; Mass spectrometry working group Ruhr-</p>	<p>From 2005-2008 there has existed two separate XML formats for</p>	<p>Mass spectrometry data</p>	<p>Released, in production</p>

			Universitat Bochum University of Liverpool, UK Université de Lyon	encoding raw spectrometer output: mzData developed by the PSI and mzXML developed at the Seattle Proteome Center at the Institute for Systems Biology. It was recognized that the existence of two separate formats for essentially the same thing generated confusion and required extra programming effort. Therefore the PSI, with full participation by ISB, has developed a		
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				<p>new format by taking the best aspects of each of the precursor formats to form a single one. It is intended to replace the previous two formats. This new format was originally given a working name of dataXML. The final name is mzML.</p>		
<p>Imaging mz Markup Language</p>	<p>imzML</p>	<p>Syntax Specification</p>	<p>imzML working group</p>	<p>The purpose of imzML is to facilitate the exchange and processing of mass spectrometry imaging data. This website is intended to</p>	<p>Mass Spectrometry based imaging data</p>	<p>Released, in production</p>

				<p>provide all information necessary to implement imzML. imzML was developed in the framework of the EU funded project COMPUTIS. The main goals during the development were complete description of MS imaging experiments and efficient storage of (very large) data sets. imzML is not limited to MS imaging, but is also useful for other MS applications generating large data</p>		
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				sets such as LC-FTMS. The current version is mzML 1.1.0. The metadata part of imzML is based on the mzML format by HUPO-PSI		
Mass Spectrometry Controlled Vocabulary	PSI-MS CV	Controlled Terminology	HUPO-PSI initiative	The PSI-Mass Spectrometry (MS) CV contains all the terms used in the PSI MS-related data standards. The CV contains a logical hierarchical structure to ensure ease of maintenance and the development of software that makes use of complex	Mass spectrometry	Released, in production

				<p>semantics. The CV contains terms required for a complete description of an MS analysis pipeline used in proteomics, including sample labeling, digestion enzymes, instrumentation parts and parameters, software used for identification and quantification of peptides/proteins and the parameters and scores used to determine their significance. Owing to the range of</p>		
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				<p>topics covered by the CV, collaborative development across several PSI working groups, including proteomics research groups, instrument manufacturers and software vendors, was necessary.</p>		
<p>Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Markup Language</p>	<p>NMR-ML</p>	<p>Syntax Specification</p>	<p>MSI Initiative</p>	<p>nmrML is an open markup language for NMR data. It is currently under heavy development and is not yet ready for public use. The development of this standard is coordinated by</p>	<p>Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy</p>	<p>Alpha version</p>

				<p>Workpackage 2 of the COSMOS - COordination Of Standards In MetabOloMi cS Project. The nmrML data standard will be approved by the Metabolomics Standards Initiative and was derived from an earlier nmrML that was developed by the Metabolomics Innovation Centre (TMIC).</p>		
<p>Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Controlled Vocabulary</p>	<p>nmrCV</p>	<p>Controlled Terminology</p>	<p>MSI Initiative</p>	<p>nmrCV is a MSI-sanctioned NMR controlled vocabulary, created</p>	<p>Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy</p>	<p>Alpha Release</p>

				within the COSMOS EU project, to support the nmrML data standard for nuclear magnetic resonance data in metabolomics with meaningful raw data descriptors.		
mz5	mz5	Syntax Specification	Alexander von Humboldt Foundation NIH	mz5 is a complete reimplementation of the mzML ontology that is based on the efficient, industrial strength storage backend HDF5.	Mass spectrometry data	Released, in production

A.2 Small molecule and chemical entity description standards

Name	Abbreviation	Type	Development Group	Description	Domain	Status
IUPAC International Chemical Identifier	InChI	Standard	InChI Trust, Cambridge, UK	Originally developed by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), the IUPAC International Chemical Identifier (InChI) is a character string generated by computer algorithm. It is a tool to be used in software applications designed and developed by those who choose to use it. The InChI algorithm turns chemical structures into machine-readable strings of information. InChIs are unique to the compound they describe and can encode absolute stereochemistry making chemicals and chemistry machine-readable and discoverable. A simple analogy is that InChI is the bar-code for chemistry and chemical structures.		Released

				<p>The InChI format and algorithm are non-proprietary and the software is open source, with ongoing development done by the community. A number of IUPAC working groups is currently creating standard for those areas of chemistry that are not yet handled by the InChI algorithm.</p>		
Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification Format	SMILES	Syntax Specification		<p>"Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification Format" is a standard, specialising in the fields described under "scope and data types", below. Until this entry is claimed, more information on this project can be found at http://www.opensmiles.org/spec/opensmiles.html. This text was generated automatically. If you work on the project responsible for "Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry Specification Format" then please consider</p>		Released

				helping us by claiming this record and updating it appropriately.		
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A.3. Clinical Data Standards

Name	Abbreviation	Type	Development Group	Description	Domain	Status
CDISC Study Data Tabulated Model	CDISC SDTM	Syntax Specification	CDISC	defines a standard structure for human clinical trial (study) data tabulations and for nonclinical study data tabulations that are to be submitted as part of a product application to a regulatory authority such as the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA)	Clinical Trial Data Regulatory Submission	Released as Production Ready
CDISC Pharmacogenomics	CDISC PGX	Syntax Specification	CDISC	An extension domain on CDISC SDTM to cover regulatory submission of biomarker discovery results and pharmacogenomics findings. Now required	Clinical Trial Pharmacogenomics Data	Released as Draft Standard for Trial Use

				by US FDA for all regulatory submissions which employ high parallel molecular biology techniques.		
CDISC Clinical Data Acquisition Standards Harmonization	CDASH	Syntax Specification	CDISC	Related to the CDISC SDTM format, CDASH defines a minimal data collection set for sixteen safety SDTM Domains, harmonizing element names, definitions and metadata. The objective is to establish a standardized data collection baseline across all submissions.	Data Collection, Clinical Trial.	Released as Production Ready
PhenoPacket	PFX	Syntax Specification	GA4GH and several major academic centers	An initiative to deliver standardize messages describing patient phenotypic information in a regularized data structure. The specification recommends using the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) and OBO Foundry resources owing to the open licensing terms. Serialization can be YAML, JSON,JSON-LD. It is under development and is being considered by the Global Alliance	Phenotype, Clinical signs.	Under Development, Initial Release June 2016

				for Genomic Health.		
Standard PREanalytical Code	SPREC	Syntax Specifica tion and Annotati on Guidelin es	ISBER	iobanks provide stored material to basic, translational and epidemiological research and this material should be transferred without institute-dependent intrinsic bias. The ISBER Biospecimen Science Working Group has released a “Standard PREanalytical Code” (SPREC), which is a proposal for a standard coding of the preanalytical options which have been adopted, in order to track and make explicit preanalytic variations in collection, preparation and storage of specimens. Each biospecimen is assigned a seven-element-long code that correspond to seven preanalytical variables and contains a string of letters(different for fluid or for solid tissues) in a defined order, separated by hypens	Patient Specim en Collecti on and preserv ation conditio ns, Bioban king format	In Productio n
HL7					Electro	

					nic health records	
Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources	HL7 FHIR	Syntax Specification		HL7 FHIR is a upgrade over HL7 CDA to give HL7 standards agility and compatibility with web standards. HL7 FHIR provides xml and JavaScript Online Notation (JSON) with an http-based RESTful protocol where each resource has predictable URL	Electronic health records	Released as Draft Standard for Trial Use
HL7 consent directive messaging	HL7 PCD	Syntax Specification		A specific extension/module in the HL7 model to capture patient consent. http://wiki.hl7.org/index.php?title=FHIR_Consent_Directive_Implementation_Guide#Examples http://hl7-fhir.github.io/	Patient Consent	Released as Draft Standard for Trial Use
HL7 consent directive messaging		Controlled Terminology		http://hl7-fhir.github.io/valueset-consent-category.html	Patient Consent	Released as Draft Standard for Trial Use
	HL7 CDA	Syntax		The Clinical Document	Electronic	Released

		Specifica tion		Architecture (CDA) is a markup standard for describing the structure and semantics of clinical documents. Developed by Health Level Seven (HL7), an organisation that develops health informatics interoperability standards, CDA forms part of the wider HL7 version 3 standard that additionally includes standards for the general implementation model and messaging framework that HP7-compliant systems adhere to.	nic health records	as Productio n Ready
Medical eXtensible Markup Language	MML	Syntax Specifica tion	NPO MedXML consortiu m	The Medical Markup Language (MML) is a language for describing different kinds of medical data, including clinical patient data, for a range of different medical fields (Kenji et al, 2000). Developed by the Japan Association for Medical Informatics “Electronic Health Record Research Group” to address interoperability when exchanging medical data between different hospitals and medical	Electro nic health records	Released as Productio n Ready (v4.0 2016)

				information providers. http://www.medxml.net/MML40j/mml4.html		
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A.4. Clinical, Phenotype and Disease Relevant Terminology

Name	Abbreviation	Type	Development Group	Description	Domain	Status
National Cancer Institute Thesaurus	NCIT	Controlled Terminology	US National Cancer Institute	The National Cancer Institute (NCI) Thesaurus is an ontology-like vocabulary that includes broad coverage of the cancer domain, including cancer related diseases, findings and abnormalities; anatomy; agents, drugs and chemicals; genes and gene products and so on. In certain areas, like cancer diseases and combination chemotherapies, it provides the most granular and consistent terminology available.	Medical Terminology, Clinical signs, cancer, phenotype	In Production
Standardized Nomenclature in Medicine	SNOMED	Controlled Terminology	The International Health Terminology Standards Development	SNOMED CT is a generic healthcare terminology together with various relations between it's over 300,000 concepts. There are about a	Medical Terminology, Clinical signs, disease, phenotype	In Production

			ent Organisati on	million descriptions of those concepts and about a million semantic links between them. SNOMED CT is one of a suite of designated standards for use in U.S. Federal Government systems for the electronic exchange of clinical health information and is also a required standard in interoperability specifications of the U.S. Healthcare Information Technology Standards Panel.	e	
Internation al Classificati on of Disease	ICD	Controll ed Termino logy	World Health Organizati on	ICD is designed to promote international comparability in the collection, processing, classification, and presentation of diagnostics in health epidemiology, health management and mortality statistics. These include the analysis of the general health situation of population groups and monitoring of the incidence and prevalence of diseases and other health problems in relation to other variables such as the characteristics and circumstances of the individuals affected.	Medical Terminol ogy, Clinical signs, disease, phenotyp e	In Produc tion

Human Phenotype Ontology	HPO	Controlled Terminology	Charite Berlin, Germany, Monarch Initiation USA, OBOFoundry	The Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) aims to provide a standardized vocabulary of phenotypic abnormalities encountered in human disease. Each term in the HPO describes a phenotypic abnormality, such as atrial septal defect. The HPO is currently being developed using the medical literature, Orphanet, DECIPHER, and OMIM. HPO currently contains approximately 11,000 terms (still growing) and over 115,000 annotations to hereditary diseases. The HPO also provides a large set of HPO annotations to approximately 4000 common diseases.	Diseases and Phenotypes	In Production
CDISC Terminology	CDISC Terminology	Controlled Terminology			Clinical Trial, Study Design, disease,	
Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes	LOINC	Controlled Terminology	Regenstrief Institute, USA	A universal code system for tests, measurements, and observations.	Laboratory Tests	In Production

A.5. Date and Units Standards

Name	Abbreviation	Type	Development Group	Description	Domain	Status
Unified Code for Units of Measure	UCUM	Controlled Terminology	Regenstrief Institute	The Unified Code for Units of Measure is a code system intended to include all units of measures being contemporarily used in international science, engineering, and business. The purpose is to facilitate unambiguous electronic communication of quantities together with their units	Unit of Measurement	In Production, adopted by CDISC, HL7, LOIN, recommended by FDA in regulatory submissions..
Data elements and interchange formats	ISO 8601	Syntax specification	ISO	ISO 8601 can be used by anyone who wants to use a standardized way of presenting dates and times. It helps cut out the uncertainty and confusion when communicating internationally. The full standard covers ways to write:	Date, Time Interval {duration, period}	In Production, adopted by CDISC, HL7, GA4GH and Phenopacket.

				Date Time of day Coordinated universal time (UTC) Local time with offset to UTC Date and time Time intervals Recurring time intervals		
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A.6 Computational Workflow Format Specification Standards

Name	Abbreviation	Type	Development Group	Description	Domain	Status
Business Process Execution Language	BPEL	Syntax Specification	OASIS	The Business Process Execution Language (BPEL) is an XML language for describing business process behaviour based on Web services. The BPEL workflow description language supports many of the features found in modern programming languages like flow control, variables, concurrent execution, input and output, transaction scoping,	Business process, workflow	Released

				compensation, and error handling. BPEL is layered on top of other Web technologies such as WSDL, XML Schema, XPath, XSLT, and WS Addressing.		
Business Process Model and Notation	BPMN	Syntax Specification	OMG	A graphical front-end to capture BPEL process descriptions, similar to concepts in UML.		Released
Common Workflow Language	CWL	Syntax Specification	CWL Community	The Common Workflow Language (CWL) is an informal, multi-vendor working group consisting of various organizations and individuals that have an interest in portability of data analysis workflows, built on technologies such as JSON-LD and Docker.	Analysis workflow	Released
Simple Conceptual Unified Flow Language	Scufl	Syntax Specification	myGrid	Developed out of the UK myGrid project, the Simple Conceptual Unified Flow Language (Scufl) is a markup language for describing workflows. Initially conceived for creating bioinformatics	workflow	Released

				workflows using the Taverna software package.		
XML Simple Conceptual Unified Flow Language	XScufl	Syntax Specification	myGrid	An XML version of the Scufl specification (XScufl) allows the definition of workflows using an XML-based vocabulary and a different enactment engine called Freeflu.	workflow	Released
Yet Another Workflow Language	YAWL	Syntax Specification	YAWL Foundation	Widely considered as an alternative to BPEL, YAWL is a workflow language based on workflow patterns and supported by an underlying open source software system including graphical editing and execution. It has been used in production-level industrial deployments such as for first:utility and first:telecom in the UK, ATOS Worldwide and the Intercontinental Hotels Group.	workflow	Released

ELSI Policies Directives and Standards

PhenoMeNal has a dedicated work package focusing on ethics and privacy requirements. Therefore, we include the recommendations made by the working group as a reminder in the present report. These recommendations are available as [deliverable document](#). PhenoMeNal Work Package 4 also made available [technical guidelines](#), which are still a work in progress owing the rapidly evolving context. We provide below a table providing key US and European legal framework documentation as an indicate of what PhenoMeNal needs to be aware of and what are the possible legal costs associated with demonstrated violations of the law.

Policy	Abbreviation	URL	Domain	Status
US Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act	HIPAA	http://www.ama-assn.org/ama/pub/physician-resources/solutions-managing-your-practice/coding-billing-insurance/hipaahealth-insurance-portability-accountability-act.page?	Data security, patient privacy	In production, Enforced
EU Directive 95/46/EC	Data Protection Directive	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:31995L0046:en:HTML	Data security	In production, Enforced
EU Directive	General Data	http://eur-	Person Privacy	In production,

2016/679	Protection Regulation (GDPR)	lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/XT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN		Enforced
UK MRC Information Security Policy		https://www.mrc.ac.uk/about/information-standards/information-security/	Data security	

As highlighted in section A3, HL7 is to our knowledge the only standard providing formal specification, supporting vocabularies as well as implementation examples to store and transmit patient consent.

B. Survey Questions Summary Results (taken from SurveyMonkey)

B.1. Survey Question Reference

Note: Choice answers presented to the survey respondent are not illustrated here for the sake of brevity. For the further details, please refer to the full dataset provided. The headings 'Clinical-related', 'Data manager', and 'Software and infra' refer to the different groups of respondents (as identified by themselves in Q3) and a 'X' indicates of the question was asked to that group. The question references where multiple question numbers are referenced indicate where the same question was asked, but in the survey logic it appears in different places. For example, Q4/60/96 is the same question, but Q4 appears in the clinical track, Q60 in the data manager track, and Q96 in the software and infrastructure track.

Reference	Question	Clinical related	Data manager	Software and infra
Q1	Your details	X	X	X
Q2	Please keep me up to date with:	X	X	X
Q3	What is your primary role or occupation (please pick closest match to your role)?	X	X	X
Q4/60/96	Which research domain or topic are you involved in?	X	X	X
Q5/61/97	What kind of studies are carried out?	X	X	X
Q6/62/98	What are you using metabolomics techniques for?	X	X	X
Q7/63/99	How many patients on average are processed each year?	X	X	X
Q8/56/92	Are you aware of regulatory constraints about Patient Consent Information disclosure?	X	X	X

Q9/57/93	What, if any, anonymization or pseudonymization procedure do you use?	X	X	X
Q10/58/94	Does your research require that you operate under specific national legal frameworks?	X	X	X
Q11/59/95	Does your research require you to operate under specific international regulation?	X	X	X
Q12/34/64	Which metabolomics platforms are you using?	X	X	X
Q13/35/65	Which applications of metabolomics do you use?	X	X	X
Q14/36/66	Do you rely on third-party service providers for metabolic analysis?	X	X	X
Q15/37/67	If using NMR, what data file format do you use?	X	X	X
Q16/38/68	If using MS, which data file format do you use?	X	X	X
Q17/39/69	What is the sample throughput at your facility or how many samples are processed by your facility on a yearly basis?	X	X	X
Q18/40/70	Do your funders mandate data sharing and data deposition?	X	X	X
Q19/41/71	Have you submitted human metabolomics data to public repositories?	X	X	X
Q20/42/72	Have you submitted research data to Data Journals, such as NPG Scientific Data or BMC	X	X	X

	GigaScience?			
Q21/43/73	Have you submitted clinical trial data to Regulatory Agencies (FDA, EMA)?	X	X	X
Q22/44/74	Are you aware of any of the following guidelines and syntax?	X	X	X
Q23/45/75	Are you aware of any of the following standards organisations?	X	X	X
Q24/46/76	What do you use for collecting your sample tracking metadata and data?	X	X	X
Q25/47/77	If using a LIMS, what vendor/manufacture provides the system?	X	X	X
Q26/48/78	If using a LIMS, what formats and what type of information can you export?	X	X	X
Q27/49/79	If using a LIMS, what patient and sample information do you record?	X	X	X
Q28/50/80	How do you currently report dates and duration? If so, do you rely on a particular standard?	X	X	X
Q29	Does your data undergo any steps to ensure integrity and protection?	X		
Q51/81	What kind of process does the data undergo to ensure integrity and protection?		X	X
Q30	Do you encrypt your data?	X		

Q52/82	Which method do you use to encrypt data?		X	X
Q31/53/83	Do you have any other needs regarding how you share or report data?	X	X	X
Q32/54/84	How do you disclose and report the data analysis procedures leading to your conclusions?	X	X	X
Q33/55/91	What, if any, other data management and processing software tools do you use in your analyses?	X	X	X
Q85	Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following NMR tools.			X
Q86	Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following GC-MS tools. If you do not k			X
Q87	Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following LC-MS tools.			X
Q88	Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following DIMS tools.			X
Q89	Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following metabolic network and/or enrichment analysis tools.			X
Q90	Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at			X

	all) the following fluxomics tools.			
Q91	What, if any, other data management and processing software tools do you use in your analyses?			X
Q100	Do you anticipate any future needs in handling metabolomics data that you do not feel are currently being addressed or talked about?	X	X	X
Q101	Please provide up to 8 search queries or use cases you consider essential to discovery and exploration of metabolomics data.	X	X	X

B.2. Survey Response Summary Tables

Summary results are provided for the survey responses in the tables in this section, from Q3 onwards (Q1 and Q2 are administrative and include personal information). Where appropriate, answers were aggregated from multiple respondent groups. The results for each separate group can be found in the full dataset provided.

Q3

What is your primary role or occupation (please pick closest match to your role)?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Clinician, clinical researcher or Principal Investigator	36.4%	48
Data manager or curator	8.3%	11
Data analysis, computation, software, infrastructure	55.3%	73

<i>answered question</i>	132
<i>skipped question</i>	0

Q4/60/96

Which research domain or topic are you involved in?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Ageing	19.0%	16
Cancer	44.0%	37
Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)	14.3%	12
Diabetes type 2 and Metabolic Syndrome	34.5%	29
Heart Disease (HD)	15.5%	13
Irritable Bowel Disease (IDB)	8.3%	7
Liver Health	21.4%	18
Nephropathy	9.5%	8
Nutrition	27.4%	23
Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA)	11.9%	10
Other (please specify)	51.2%	43
<i>answered question</i>		84
<i>skipped question</i>		312

Q5/61/97

What kind of studies are carried out?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Intervention studies	57.3%	47
Longitudinal observation studies	52.4%	43
Repeated measure studies (cross-over design)	34.1%	28
Meta-analysis	19.5%	16
In-silico modeling	25.6%	21
Other (please specify)	18.3%	15
<i>answered question</i>		82
<i>skipped question</i>		314

Q6/62/98

What are you using metabolomics techniques for?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Global profiling studies	82.8%	72
Targeted profiling studies	71.3%	62
Stable isotope resolved studies	20.7%	18
Imaging application of metabolomics	14.9%	13
Other (please specify)	2.5%	2
<i>answered question</i>		87
<i>skipped question</i>		309

Q7/63/99

How many patients on average are processed each year?	
Answer Options	Response Count
>1,000	19
1,000-10,000	7
10,000-100,000	2
>100,000	7
<i>answered question</i>	
37	
<i>skipped question</i>	
11	

Q8/56/92

Are you aware of regulatory constraints about Patient Consent Information disclosure?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes, fully aware	39.8%	33
Yes, but do not know the binding details	37.3%	31
No	22.9%	19
<i>answered question</i>		83

skipped question **313**

Q9/57/93 – see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

What, if any, anonymization or pseudonymization procedure do you use?		
Answer Options	Answer Options	Response Count
		36
	<i>answered question</i>	36
	<i>skipped question</i>	360

Q10/58/94

Does your research require that you operate under specific national legal frameworks? If yes, please specify which ones.		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes	49.2%	31
No	46.0%	29
Additional information (please specify)		20
	<i>answered question</i>	63
	<i>skipped question</i>	333

Q11/59/95

Does your research require you to operate under specific international regulation? If yes, please specify which ones.		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes	30.0%	18
No	70.0%	42
Additional information (please specify)		11
answered question		60
skipped question		336

Q12/34/64

Which metabolomics platforms are you using?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) , 1D, 2D, Hyphenated derivatives	31.7%	32
Mass spectrometry (MS), (MS)n, LC-MS, GC-MS, Hyphenated derivatives	86.1%	87
Liquid chromatography (LC)	38.6%	39
Fluxomics	14.9%	15
Colorimetry	1.0%	1
Other (please specify)	5.0%	5
answered question		101
skipped question		295

Q13/35/65

Which applications of metabolomics do you use?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Global profiling studies	85.6%	83
Targeted profiling studies	67.0%	65
Stable isotope resolved studies	24.7%	24
Imaging application of metabolomics	12.4%	12
Other (please specify)	3.1%	3
<i>answered question</i>		97
<i>skipped question</i>		299

Q14/36/66

Which applications of metabolomics do you use?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Global profiling studies	85.6%	83
Targeted profiling studies	67.0%	65
Stable isotope resolved studies	24.7%	24
Imaging application of metabolomics	12.4%	12
Other (please specify)	3.1%	3

<i>answered question</i>	97
<i>skipped question</i>	299

Q15/37/67

If using NMR, what data file format do you use?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Bruker file format	78.4%	29
Agilent Variant format	18.9%	7
Joel format	5.4%	2
Open source nmrML	13.5%	5
JCAMP-DX	13.5%	5
Other (please specify)	13.5%	5
<i>answered question</i>		37
<i>skipped question</i>		359

Q16/38/68

If using MS, which data file format do you use?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
wiff	33.3%	14
mzML	75.0%	56

imzML	8.3%	5
netCDF	41.7%	38
HDF5	8.3%	6
mz5	8.3%	2
Other (please specify)	16.7%	27
answered question		85
skipped question		311

Q17/39/69

What is the sample throughput at your facility or how many samples are processed by your facility on a yearly basis?	
Answer Options	Response Count
>1,000	12
1,000-10,000	32
10,000-100,000	11
>100,000	2
answered question	
49	
skipped question	
8	

Q18/40/70

Do your funders mandate data sharing and data deposition?		
Answer Options	Respons	Respon

	e Percent	se Count
Yes, with no restrictions	9.9%	8
Yes, but with access control due to patient privacy concerns	38.3%	31
No	34.6%	28
Don't know and need to check	17.3%	14
<i>answered question</i>		81
<i>skipped question</i>		315

Q19/41/71

Have you submitted human metabolomics data to public repositories?		
Answer Options	Respon e Percent	Respon se Count
Yes, to EMBL-EBI Metabolights	19.8%	16
Yes, to NIH Metabolomics Workbench	3.7%	3
Yes, to our national archive or institutional repository	2.5%	2
Yes, to another repository (please specify in additional information below)	9.9%	8
No, and I never tried	42.0%	34
No, I can not disclose data publicly for legal reasons (patent, patient privacy concerns, national laws)	11.1%	9
No, for other reasons (please specify in additional information below)	17.3%	14
Additional information (please specify)	25.9%	21
<i>answered question</i>		81

skipped question 315

Q20/42/72

Have you submitted research data to Data Journals, such as NPG Scientific Data or BMC GigaScience?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes	8.5%	7
No	74.4%	61
I don't know what a Data Journal is	17.1%	14
<i>answered question</i>		82
<i>skipped question</i>		314

Q21/43/73

Have you submitted clinical trial data to Regulatory Agencies (FDA, EMA)?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes, we used CDISC for metadata or data submission	0.0%	0
No, but I will soon need to	7.6%	6
No, and never tried	86.1%	68
I don't know what complying with regulatory submission entails	3.8%	3
Other (please specify)	2.5%	2
<i>answered question</i>		79

skipped question 317

Q22/44/74

Are you aware of any of the following guidelines and syntax?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Study Data Tabulation Model (STDM)	11.9%	5
Investigation, Study, Assay (ISA) format	57.1%	24
Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)	4.8%	2
Standard PREanalytical Coding for biospecimens (SPREC) guidelines	4.8%	2
Core Information for Metabolomics Reporting (CIMR) Guidelines	47.6%	20
Other (please specify)	21.4%	9
<i>answered question</i>		42
<i>skipped question</i>		354

Q23/45/75

Are you aware of any of the following standards organisations?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Metabolomics Standards Initiative (MSI)	89.4%	59
Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC)	6.1%	4

Health Level 7 (HL7)	9.1%	6
Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT)	7.6%	5
Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)	10.6%	7
International Society for Biological and Environmental Repositories (ISBER)	6.1%	4
Metabolomics Society Data Standards Task Group	63.6%	42
Other (please specify)	9.1%	6
answered question		66
skipped question		330

Q24/46/76

What do you use for collecting your sample tracking metadata and data?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Custom built LIMS system	31.0%	22
Commercial LIMS system	5.6%	4
SiLA standard compatible system	1.4%	1
Excel spreadsheet	77.5%	55
Paper	8.5%	6
Other (please specify)	15.5%	11
answered question		71
skipped question		325

Q25/47/77 – see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

If using a LIMS, what vendor/manufacturer provides the system?	
Answer Options	Response Count
	11
<i>answered question</i>	11
<i>skipped question</i>	385

Q26/48/78

If using a LIMS, what formats and what type of information can you export?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
CSV or TSV files	86.7%	26
JSON	20.0%	6
XML	36.7%	11
Analytical Information Markup Language (AniML) Format	3.3%	1
LIMS specific API	13.3%	4
Database dump	13.3%	4
Other (please specify)	10.0%	3
<i>answered question</i>		30
<i>skipped question</i>		366

Q27/49/79

If using a LIMS, what patient and sample information do you record?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Fully integrated to a clinical database	10.7%	3
Basic information (patient id, patient age, patient gender', sample id and sample type)	17.9%	5
Customized for each project, highly variable	57.1%	16
None, only an autogenerated specimen ID used as key	17.9%	5
Other (please specify)	14.3%	4
<i>answered question</i>		28
<i>skipped question</i>		368

Q28/50/80

How do you currently report dates and duration? If so, do you rely on a particular standard?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Free text	52.7%	29
Custom format	34.5%	19
ISO8601 compliant reporting (YYYY:MM:DD T:hh:mm:ss as in 2016-01-11T17:31:10)	20.0%	11
Other (please specify)	5.5%	3
<i>answered question</i>		55
<i>skipped question</i>		341

Q29

Does your data undergo any steps to ensure integrity and protection? If so, please specify.		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes	42.1%	8
No	26.3%	5
Additional information (please specify)	31.6%	6
<i>answered question</i>		19
<i>skipped question</i>		113

Q51/81

What kind of process does the data undergo to ensure integrity and protection?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
MD5 hashing	2.2%	1
SHA1 hashing	4.4%	2
SHA2 hashing	0.0%	0
SHA3 hashing	0.0%	0
No such process in place	46.7%	21
Don't know	44.4%	20

Other (please specify)	2.2%	1
answered question		45
skipped question		219

Q30

Do you encrypt your data? If so, please specify any additional information on how.		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Yes	19.0%	4
No	81.0%	17
Additional information (please specify)		0
answered question		21
skipped question		111

Q52/82

Which method do you use to encrypt data?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
AES128	0.0%	0
AES192	0.0%	0
AES 256	0.0%	0
DES	0.0%	0

Triple DES 56	0.0%	0
Triple DES 112	0.0%	1
Triple DES 168	0.0%	0
No encryption	80.0%	33
Don't know	20.0%	13
Other (please specify)		2
<i>answered question</i>		45
<i>skipped question</i>		219

Q31/53/83 – see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

Do you have any other needs regarding how you share or report data?	
Answer Options	Response Count
	7
<i>answered question</i>	7
<i>skipped question</i>	389

Q32/54/84

How do you disclose and report the data analysis procedures leading to your conclusions?		
Answer Options	Response Percent	Response Count
Textual description and references in the manuscript	67.1%	47

R script/application	45.7%	32
Matlab script/application	14.3%	10
Galaxy workflow	2.9%	2
Knime workflow	5.7%	4
Workflow4Metabolomics	7.1%	5
No disclosure	2.9%	2
Other (please specify)	12.9%	9
answered question		70
skipped question		326

Q33/55/91– see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

What, if any, other data management and processing software tools do you use in your analyses?	
Answer Options	Response Count
	23
answered question	23
skipped question	373

Q85

Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following NMR tools. If you do not know the tool, please use N/A.								
Answer Options	essential (1)	very important	important (3)	not that important	not important	N/A	Rating Ave	Response Count

		(2)		rtant (4)	at all (5)		rage	
Vnmrj (Agilent)	1	0	1	1	2	2 2	3.60	27
Topspin (Bruker)	9	3	2	0	1	1 4	1.73	29
AMIX (Bruker)	3	0	4	1	3	1 7	3.09	28
NMRLab/MetaboLab (in Matlab)	0	1	1	0	3	2 2	4.00	27
ACD NMR manager (ACD Labs)	0	1	3	5	2	1 8	3.73	29
Mnova NMR (Mestrelab Research)	1	1	3	2	1	2 1	3.13	29
ProMetab (in Matlab)	0	2	1	0	1	2 4	3.00	28
rNMR (in R)	0	0	1	2	2	2 4	4.20	29
Workflow4Metabolomics	0	2	6	0	1	2 0	3.00	29
<i>answered question</i>								29
<i>skipped question</i>								103

Q86

Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following GC-MS tools. If you do not know the tool, please use N/A.

Answer Options	essential (1)	very important (2)	important (3)	not that important (4)	not important at all (5)	N / A	Rating Average	Response Count
AMDIS	4	2	3	1	0	23	2.10	33
Xcalibur (Thermo)	2	3	2	2	2	21	2.91	32
ChromaTof (Leco)	1	0	2	2	2	27	3.57	34
Chemstation (Agilent)	2	2	4	6	1	18	3.13	33
GCMSSolutions (Shimadzu)	0	0	1	2	1	29	4.00	33
Metabolite Detector	0	0	1	2	0	30	3.67	33
metAlign	1	2	3	2	1	24	3.00	33
MetaMS (R Based)	1	1	2	1	0	27	2.60	32
XCMS	11	6	2	4	1	11	2.08	35
Met-Idea	2	0	0	2	0	27	2.50	31
Workflow4Metabolomics	4	3	4	1	0	22	2.17	34
answered question								36
skipped question								96

Q87

Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following LC-MS tools. If you do not know the tool, please use N/A.

Answer Options	essential (1)	very important (2)	important (3)	not that important (4)	not important at all (5)	N / A	Rating Average	Response Count
AnalyzerPro (SpectralWorks)	0	0	1	2	2	32	4.20	37
MassHunter (Agilent)	2	2	6	3	3	22	3.19	38
MAVEN	0	0	3	4	0	30	3.57	37
metAlign	0	2	6	4	2	21	3.43	35
MZmine and MZmine2	2	5	10	5	4	9	3.15	35
MassLynx (Waters)	3	1	5	4	2	21	3.07	36
Progenesis QI (Waters/Nonlinear Dynamics)	3	1	3	3	2	25	3.00	37
SIEVE or Compound Discoverer (Thermo Scientific)	1	0	4	4	2	26	3.55	37
XCMS	21	8	5	0	1	6	1.63	41
XCMS Online	3	3	7	9	4	1	3.31	38

						2		
XCMS Plus (Sciex)	0	0	1	5	2	26	4.13	34
Analyst, Peak View (Sciex)	2	0	3	2	1	30	3.00	38
MS-DIAL	2	2	2	0	0	30	2.00	36
Spectronaut (Biognosys)	0	0	0	1	0	34	4.00	35
OpenMS	3	5	5	0	3	19	2.69	35
MzR	4	2	5	1	0	24	2.25	36
Workflow4Metabolomics	4	9	4	0	1	21	2.17	39
answered question								41
skipped question								91

Q88

Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following DIMS tools. If you do not know the tool, please use N/A.								
Answer Options	essential (1)	very important (2)	important (3)	not that important (4)	not important at all (5)	N / A	Rating Average	Response Count
SIM-stitch (in	0	0	0	1	1	30	4.50	32

Matlab)									
SIEVE or Compo und Discov erer (Therm o Scientif ic)	0	0	0	2	1	2	4.33	31	
						8			
	7	1	6	0	2	1	2.31	32	
XCMS						6			
XCMS Online	1	1	5	3	2	2	3.33	32	
						0			
answered question									32
skipped question									100

Q89

Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following metabolic network and/or enrichment analysis tools. If you do not know the tool, please use N/A.

Answer Options	esse ntial (1)	very impo rtant (2)	impo rtant (3)	not that impo rtant (4)	not impo rtant at all (5)	N / A	Rati ng Ave rage	Response Count
Cytoscape	8	8	5	2	2	1 3	2.28	38
IMPALA	0	0	2	4	1	2 7	3.86	34

Ingenuity IPA	0	2	3	4	2	2	3.55	35
MetaboAnalyst	2	6	7	5	1	1	2.86	36
MetaMapR	2	2	1	0	1	2	2.33	35
MetExplore	5	2	5	0	1	2	2.23	38
MetNet	1	0	0	0	0	3	1.00	33
Pathway Tools Omics Viewer	1	0	2	1	0	3	2.75	36
Workflow4Metabolomics	2	4	3	3	0	2	2.58	38
answered question								38
skipped question								94

Q90

Please rate on a scale of 1 (essential) to 5 (not important at all) the following fluxomics tools. If you do not know the tool, please use N/A.

Answer Options	essential (1)	very important (2)	important (3)	not that important (4)	not important at all (5)	N / A	Rating Average	Response Count
13C	0	1	1	0	0	2	2.50	31
FiatFlux	0	1	1	1	0	2	3.00	31

iMAT	0	1	0	0	0	3	2.00	31
						0		
INCA	0	1	0	0	0	2	2.00	30
						9		
isodesign	0	1	0	0	0	2	2.00	30
						9		
metran	0	1	0	0	0	3	2.00	31
						0		
OpenFlux	0	1	0	0	0	3	2.00	31
						0		
OpenFlux 2	0	1	1	0	0	2	2.50	31
						9		
OpenMoe bius	0	1	0	0	0	3	2.00	31
						0		
Fluxomer Iterative Algorithm	0	1	0	0	0	2	2.00	30
						9		
<i>answered question</i>								31
<i>skipped question</i>								101

Q91 – see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

What, if any, other data management and processing software tools do you use in your analyses?	
Answer Options	Response Count
	14
<i>answered question</i>	
	14
<i>skipped question</i>	
	118

Q100 – see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

Do you anticipate any future needs in handling metabolomics data that you do not feel are currently being addressed or talked about?	
Answer Options	Response Count
	27
<i>answered question</i>	27
<i>skipped question</i>	105

Q101 – see data sheets for raw responses (all free text).

Please provide up to 8 search queries or use cases you consider essential to discovery and exploration of metabolomics data.	
Answer Options	Response Count
	21
<i>answered question</i>	21
<i>skipped question</i>	111

C. Survey Dissemination Examples

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PhenoMeNal-H2020 Retweeted
Philippe Rocca-Serra @Phi_at_OeRC · Jul 21
 Thanks to @varsha_khodiyar and @alhufton and @ScientificData for their help on #metabolomics #standards #PhnmIH2020

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PhenoMeNal

Guest posting: Building a PhenoMeNal metabolomics e-infrastructure...
 Feedback required from the PhenoMeNal consortium on the requirements for medical metabolomics e-infrastructure.
 blogs.biomedcentral.com

PhenoMeNal-H2020 @PhnmIH2020 · Jul 20
 The journal @GigaScience has kindly published a guest blog post about our project and data survey

GigaScience @GigaScience
 Calling all #metabolomics researchers: PhenoMeNal are seeking community feedback. See the GigaBlog guest posting blogs.biomedcentral.com/gigablog/2016/...

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#fav7horses
 1,721 Tweets

North Korean
 5,391 Tweets

Manus Island
 7,060 Tweets

'Mr' and 'Mrs'
 2,960 Tweets